

Detection of a $10^5 M_{\odot}$ Black Hole in M31's Most Massive Globular Cluster

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Figure 1. The location of the cluster in the Andromeda galaxy. The HST image of B023-G078 on the right is composed from the F814W and F606W filters. Credit: (left) Iván Éder, <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2022ApJ...924...48P/abstract>, (right) STScI/HST.

Intermediate-mass black holes (IMBHs) are elusive objects that fall within the mass range $\geq 10^2 M_{\odot}$ and $\leq 10^5 M_{\odot}$, bracketed by stellar-mass black holes (BHs) at the low end and supermassive BHs at the high end. They are most likely to exist in the centers of globular clusters or nuclei of dwarf galaxies. Theoretically, IMBHs can be formed through different formation mechanisms including the direct collapse of gas, mergers and accretion of stellar-mass BHs, or the collapse of high-mass stars in the early Universe. Finding and weighing IMBHs can help us constrain their formation; this can be done either by detecting accretion emission or through dynamical detection. However, observations of IMBHs are challenging, due to the lack of unique signatures of BH accretion in many accretion cases and the ambiguity in distinguishing whether the central dark mass is an IMBH or a collection of stellar-mass BHs in the dynamical case. Dynamical measurements are also limited by our ability to resolve the velocity dispersions within the sphere of influence of the BH, which drives us to the closest targets. Here we discuss our recent detection [1] of an IMBH in a massive star cluster in M31. At just $10^5 M_{\odot}$, this object is the strongest candidate for an IMBH in this mass regime and a potentially valuable clue for understanding the formation of massive BHs.

Using Gemini North's adaptive-optics Near-Infrared Integral Field Spectrometer (NIFS), we were able to obtain data at the

center of B023-G078, the most massive cluster in the Andromeda galaxy (Figure 1). The high resolution of these observations ($0.13''$) was made possible using laser guide star adaptive optics with the ALTAIR system. This resulted in detection of some individual stars in this cluster, which were removed before deriving the kinematic maps shown in Figure 2. We received these data under Director's Discretionary Time shortly after the discovery of supermassive BHs in very massive stripped nuclei in the Virgo cluster by our team. B023-G078, as the most massive cluster in the Andromeda galaxy and with a visible spread in the color of its RGB stars, seemed likely to be a stripped galaxy nucleus. However, it was much less massive than the other stripped nuclei where we had detected BHs. If these lower-mass stripped galaxy nuclei host BHs, they will contribute substantially to the number density of massive BHs in the Universe.

To test whether B023-G078 hosts a central BH and to estimate its mass, we created a stellar mass model of the cluster using the light of the stars from the HST data (Figure 1). By deprojecting this mass model, we can estimate the velocity dispersion profile of the stars around the center. Using Jeans models, we found that the velocity dispersion at the center of the cluster in the observed kinematics from Gemini/NIFS was higher than what was expected based on the stellar mass model. This high-velocity dispersion indicated

Figure 2. The radial velocity and velocity dispersion maps from the Gemini/NIFS kinematic data with a spaxel size of $0.05''$. Credit: *The Astrophysical Journal* [1]

some kind of dark mass, which could either be explained by a single IMBH or by a distribution of stellar-mass BHs. The best-fit models favored the case of an IMBH with a mass of $\sim 10^5 M_{\odot}$ (Figure 3). We also modeled the cluster with an extended collection of stellar-mass BHs at the center, but our best-fit models suggest that the source is unresolved. We also found additional evidence that this object was a stripped galaxy nucleus, which supported the case for an IMBH:

- (1) The cluster has a two-component profile with varying flattening as would be expected for the nucleus of a stripped dwarf galaxy.
- (2) The rotation of the cluster was similar to that of the nuclear star clusters in galaxies, which are dense clusters at the centers of galaxies.
- (3) The metallicity of the cluster had a spread similar to that of Omega-Cen and M54, which are globular clusters or stripped nuclei bound to the Milky Way. It also varied along with the radius, with the stars at the center being more metal-rich than those in the outskirts.

All of this evidence strongly suggested that B023-G078 was a stripped nucleus. Therefore, we prefer an IMBH interpretation of the data.

Although many potential IMBH candidates exist, the kinematic data for B023-G078 suggest a strong, $>3\sigma$ detection. There is no evidence in existing archival radio and X-ray data

Figure 3. The best-fit models suggest an IMBH with a mass of $\sim 10^5 M_{\odot}$. These are the Jeans models that model the velocities of the stars using the light profile and then compare them with the kinematics. Credit: *The Astrophysical Journal* [1]

for any BH accretion, but a detection at these wavelengths could confirm the presence of a single IMBH instead of a collection of stellar-mass BHs.

Our future work includes observations with Gemini/NIFS to look at three other clusters in the Andromeda galaxy using a similar analysis to find any potential IMBHs.

Reference:

- [1] Pechetti, R., et al. 2022, *ApJ*, 924, 48